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“MODERN TEACHING METHODS”

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ANNOTATION: Nowadays we can meet the phrase “modern teaching” not only in teaching foreign languages, but also in all subjects of education such as mathematics, literature, history, geography, and other subjects of education. Simply said, modern teaching means to attract pupils by using new techniques, new methods. Now English teachers have always been concerned about the inadequacy of conventional methods of English teaching in Uzbek education systems. The teacher of 21 century should use traditional concepts and techniques of classroom teaching and should adopt the recent and innovative teaching techniques.

Key words: modern teaching techniques, problems in teaching, BST, types of learning.

Theme: Modern Teaching Methods

“The teaching method which focuses more on teaching the students for improving their intellect behavior by using various new and innovative ideas rather than making them recite the syllabus to clear the examination with the same old style is **Modern Teaching Methods** in simple words.”

The new teaching method which we called the modern teaching method is more activity-based and centres the learner’s mind which involves them entirely into the process of learning. In the modern teaching method, curriculum teaching and planning are done keeping the learner as the primary target.

Through this way, learners actively participate in the whole process to build their knowledge and sharpen their skills; this is also termed as a constructivist approach. On the other hand, the mentor or teacher only leads them and guides them to focus on the objectives of the subject. This is all done by engaging in activities and by adopting innovative modern teaching techniques. New demand of the era or the need of the hour for students is to embrace the contemporary teaching methods which will also help in reducing the competition among the students, promote cooperation, and boost the health study environment.

Brief Introduction

Over the years, there have been visible changes in teaching style. Opposite to the memorization and same old recitation practice to teach the students, now with Advantages of modern teaching methods, interactive methods of teaching have been introduced, and its result can be seen. This is an education reform which provides an entirely different angle of teaching and learning because modern teaching methods do not treat all students at the same level of their understanding ability, unlike the conventional method of teaching. Rather than the only teacher based, modern teaching methods focus more on questioning, demonstration, explaining, practical, collaboration methods, and are more activity-based.

Why modern teaching is the need of the hour?

Education is the need of the hour as it creates a literate society and in the process of educating the society, motivation and instructions are very crucial and teachers, guides and administrators are responsible to motivate learners. The rate of literacy will be leveled up by providing education to the most parts of society.

However, with time being changed to an extent, learners demand new techniques and methods to gain knowledge which specializes them not only in theoretical study but ensures them to provide practical knowledge, sharpen their skills, and make them educated to face any kind of challenges. Modern teaching methods are the only way to meet the requirements of modern times.

Modern teaching unquestionably is the need of the hour because of its relevance in the modern era. The revolution in the field of science and technology demands great ideas and extensive effort to deal with any kind of circumstances coming in the way of development. All the load is on the little shoulders of learners. So, it is vital to give students not only knowledge but to improve their skills from the very beginning.

Characteristics of Modern Teaching Methods

The modern teaching methods help to build or develop a productive understanding of basic science and technology (BST). Hence, the elements of contemporary teaching methods include:

1. Learner-centered

One of the essential characteristics of the modern teaching methods in basic science and technology (BST) is it is learner-centred. It focuses on learners while using or applying during classroom and laboratory lectures. The teacher acts only as a guide, and all the learning process involves learners. Learners significantly appear as a dominator in classroom interactions.

2. Task-Based or Activity-based

The teacher or guide of BST organizes activity or task and engages students to learn through this way. Hence it is an activity-based or commission-based. Students are offered or asked to take part in classroom interaction through these interactive activities.

3. Resource-Based

BST teachers should be resourceful. They should collect and distribute all the required study material to the learners for their learning or to understand the topic clearly. The resources can be collected from the school environment or any other place where it is available. Also, a learner can be the source to bring study material or resources from their end.

4. Interactive in Nature

One characteristic defines the modern teaching method as very interactive. The teacher asks the students to form small groups or work as individuals to perform the learning tasks and come up with the desired results. It helps them to gather knowledge from one another. Students learn to work together and a sense of cooperation. It also works in their favour when they step out in the outer world.

5. Integrative in Nature

One of the vital characteristics of Advantages of modern teaching methods is it is integrative. Teachers link topics of one subject, e.g., social science topics like drug use, domestic violence, safety, pollution, food distribution, crime etc. to other issues and make it integrative. By this, a learner can gain knowledge of more topics studying one.

6. Peer Collaboration

Modern teaching methods not only encourage students by allowing them to present their ideas or initiative by noticing their responses, studying their research, and allowing them to answer during interaction in BST classes but also selects students based on interest, needs, and feelings. Through Instructional activities, students learn to work cooperatively, and they appreciate their competitors' work as well. In the BST curriculum, learner's interests are considered most important, and they are guided towards their goals and careers.

Modern Teaching Methods are following:

Collaborative Learning

Earlier, when students were asked to revise the topic or syllabus during an examination or regular days, they used to revise the syllabus in isolation or at home. This practise was widespread in traditional teaching methods. To deal with this issue

or provide a more useful platform for students, schools are coming up with collaborative learning. In this modern teaching method, teachers form a group of students where they can solve their problem, debates on topics, and clear their queries. This helps in developing social skills and allows students to understand the subject faster.

In this modern teaching method, every student is a part of the success of a group as they help each other to reach the desired result, and they also learn to communicate with each other. Learners learn to tolerate others, develop skills to listen to others and how to work in a team. They will be able to meet different personalities and can get a genuine review of their work.

Spaced Learning

Spaced learning is one of the modern teaching methods, which is being followed by teachers. In this method, teachers repeat a lesson multiple times, basically until the students understand entirely. However, the teacher repeats the course with two 10-minute spaces (break) in-between the lessons.

The gap is meant to refresh the mind by playing physical activities or mindfulness techniques which prepares them for the next session of the same lesson. This method gives the students intervals to inherit the knowledge and create connections between learnings. Before moving forward to another chapter, this method prepares the students with basics.

Flipped Classroom

Flipped Classroom is a well-known term in the pedagogical method. You have known about this undoubtedly. Its name 'Flipped Classroom' makes it unique. It is one of the very vital modern teaching methods that has been in use these days. In this method of teaching, the teaching procedure takes place in a flipped manner.

As unlike traditional ways, students study new material or content at home by themselves and practice the same at school. The method is the reverse of providing content at school and asks students to rework on it or practice it at home. The students practice this method at home by watching a video tutorial, search online, or work on the content usually shared by the teacher. They do not need to complete the homework at home. Instead, they end it at school.

Self-learning

Curiosity pushes the learner to learn new and more always. It drives the learners to learn and memorize large spaces of the text that they will either miss gratefully or forget immediately. Through their curiosity, students get motivated to explore the subjects they are interested in. Teaching students to operate the internet and find results themselves helps them to be self-dependent and gives them a deep understanding of the content.

A teacher should allow the students to bring new ideas and work on it for the development of their brain and ability to work alone. This modern teaching method plays a significant role in learners' period of education.

Gamification

It is a well-known fact that children love games either it is online games or playing games at the field. Teaching through games is one of the essential modern teaching methods that has been in use under modern teaching ways. The significance of Gamification in teaching has mostly been seen in the elementary and preschool system. Learning through playing games won't be even realized by students. It motivated students as well and proved effective not only to the students of preschool but of any age.

The responsibility of teaching through Gamification is of teachers as they should plan or design projects that will be suitable for the students of their respective age. They should incorporate attractive measures to connect the students for a longer time and keep their interest alive. Teachers can also take help of the online platform under Gamification. Teachers can organize online quiz, puzzles or brain games. This modern teaching method is a fun learning method to teach.

VAK teaching

VAK is a modern teaching method whose effects can be seen clearly. We divide learner into three categories: Visual, Audio, and kinesthetic (movement). One needs to recognize to which category they belong to or the teacher must know to which category her students relate to.

In VAK, V is visual means seeing the data, A is Audio means gathering information by hearing the data, and K is Kinesthetic means feeling the data. A teacher should keep the category of students in kind while teaching because some students catch the information by seeing, by hearing or by feeling. So, they should present the same material in different ways.